

Original article

A preliminary study of using greener materials including deep eutectic solvents (DESS) for the cleaning of silver tarnish

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ABSTRACT

We present a preliminary study of the cleaning of artificially tarnished silver mock-ups with several greener materials, including sodium glycinate, ethylenediamine-N,N'-disuccinic acid (EDDS), saponin, and deep eutectic solvents (DESS), in comparison to a commercial silver polish product. While sodium glycinate, EDDS and saponin did not show substantial cleaning effects on light silver tarnish, a two-step method combining (i) oxidative DESS and (ii) sodium glycinate-based suspension proved effective for the removal of heavy tarnish. However, observations via colorimetry, interferometry microscopy, optical microscopy, and scanning electron microscopy showed that this two-step method could lead to surface roughening. While clear scratches and over-polishing issues were observed on coupon surfaces cleaned by the commercial silver polish product, the use of a slurry composed of sodium glycinate, citric acid, glycerol and water resulted in optimal cleaning effects, despite its relatively low cleaning rate.

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1. Introduction and research aim

Silver (Ag) has been extensively employed in history due to its excellent ductility, malleability, and brilliant metallic lustre [1]. Unfortunately, silver tarnishes quickly due to its vulnerability to invasive species such as sulphur in the atmosphere, leading to surface darkening and a reduction of metal gloss [2]. As silver is a soft material, alloying elements especially copper (Cu) are often introduced to increase the material's hardness and durability. Many historical silver objects thus have an elemental composition closer to sterling silver (92.5 wt% Ag, 7.5 wt% Cu) [3]. Since Cu oxidizes more preferably than Ag, the tarnish composition of sterling silver contains Cu–Ag–S and Cu-rich products such as stromeyerite (Ag₂CuS), jalpaite (Ag₃CuS₂), chalcocite (Cu₂S) and covellite (CuS), in addition to the main tarnishing product of pure silver – acanthite (Ag₂S) [4,5].

To improve the aesthetics of silver objects, various cleaning protocols have been applied since ancient times. However, the past few decades have yielded little progress in the development of such cleaning methods [6]. Furthermore, most cleaning methods

that have been widely used so far, including abrasive slurries, silver dips, and electro-chemical reduction [6], are not readily biodegradable. Following the global trend of sustainability, there is an increasing need for the development of greener formulations with bio-derived materials for silver cleaning in the field of conservation. For example, a greener method using alkaline solutions of sodium glycinate has been proposed, based on the complexation of Ag and Cu ions by deprotonated glycine [7,8]. Some also argue that ethylenediamine-N,N'-disuccinic acid (EDDS), a green alternative of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), has cleaning effects on tarnished sterling silver due to its high affinity towards Cu [9]. A traditional silver cleaning medium derived from plants, namely soap-nut decoction, is still widely used due to its dust removal and degreasing function as well as optimal cleaning effects on light silver tarnish [10,11]. Its main component, saponins, are natural surfactants, which show a high affinity towards heavy metals and thus have been extensively used in environmental remediation [12].

In this study, we first tested aqueous solutions of the three aforementioned complexing agents (i.e., sodium glycinate, EDDS, and saponin), which were loaded onto Evolon® microfilament tissue [13] and applied to artificially tarnished sterling and pure silver coupons. The use of a flexible loading matrix facilitated easy application on curved surfaces, which are common in metal objects. The application was further supported with agar gel in some experiments. Meanwhile, we developed a two-step cleaning method

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combining oxidative and complexing agents, taking advantage of unique features of deep eutectic solvents (DESs), a new generation of green solvents. This was inspired by a traditional chemical cleaning medium consisting of potassium nitrate and citric acid, in which potassium nitrate functions as an oxidative agent, and citric acid works as a complexing agent [14]. While DESs exhibit the properties of ionic liquids such as low vapor pressure, electric conductivity, high chemical and thermal stability and improved designability, they have further advantages including easy preparation, reduced toxicity, more biodegradability, lower environmental impacts and lower costs [15]. DESs are usually prepared from a hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA) and a hydrogen bond donor (HBD), where the charge delocalization caused by the hydrogen bond interaction leads to a reduction of the melting point [16]. Although DESs are already employed in various fields including analytical chemistry, solvent extraction, heavy metal extraction, electrochemistry, biocatalysis, biosensors, nanotechnology and pharmacy [15,17], their use in the field of conservation has so far been very limited. There are only a few exceptions where DESs have been applied in conservation contexts, such as temporary consolidation media for archaeological objects or as cleaning agents for degraded painting varnish or gelatin coatings on cinematographic films [18–20]. Only recently have acid-based DESs been introduced to the cleaning of corrosion products on copper and iron objects [21,22]. In this study, choline chloride- and iron hexahydrate-based DESs (as oxidative agent) and sodium glycinate hydrate-based DESs or suspension (as complexing agent) were loaded on Evolon tissues and then applied onto artificially tarnished sterling silver and pure silver coupons. Furthermore, a slurry composed of sodium glycinate, citric acid, glycerol and water was also tested for cleaning purposes. This formulation was designed to introduce an abrasive function for comparison to the two-step method.

This study represents the first attempt to employ DESs as a greener method for the cleaning of silver tarnish. The colour changes of the coupons after cleaning were assessed using colorimetry, while interferometric microscopy (IM) provided quantitative data on surface roughness. The surface morphology of tested coupons was observed through optical microscopy (OM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) and Raman spectroscopy were employed for the identification of tarnish composition and possible complexation compounds.

The study aims to fill a knowledge gap within the frame of sustainable conservation of historical metals and to demonstrate the combination of green chemistry and conservation practice. It is expected to provide important and reliable references for similar studies in the conservation field.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

Samples used in the study mainly consisted of sterling silver and pure silver coupons with a size of 20 × 20 × 0.5 mm (GyR Edelmetalle, Switzerland). The coupons were semi-polished by the manufacturer, exhibiting a slightly lower surface finish level than a mirror-like finish. The coupons were tarnished by suspension above a 20 % (w/v) albumin solution (AS) in a sealed glass container placed in a pre-heated oven at 75 °C for 3, 10 and 15 h respectively, to produce light, medium and heavy tarnish [23]. The resulting tarnish exhibited a high degree of homogeneity and reproducibility [23]. XRD measurements revealed that when the sterling silver coupons were aged for a few hours (e.g., 5 h), the tarnish composition mainly consisted of stromeyerite (CuAgS); after 10 h of aging, the tarnish composition consisted of stromeyerite (CuAgS), jalpaite (Ag₃CuS₂) and the sub-sulphide Ag₈S [24]. When the coupons were aged for 15 h, both CuAgS and Ag₃CuS₂ were no

longer detected; instead, the tarnish composition mainly consisted of Cu-rich and Ag-rich products [24].

Reference powder samples of silver chloride (AgCl) was purchased from Carl Roth, Switzerland.

2.2. Cleaning media

Sodium glycinate hydrate (H₂NCH₂CO₂Na·H₂O), 35 % (w/w) solution of EDDS trisodium (C₁₀H₁₃N₂Na₃O₈), saponin powder, sodium thiosulphate (Na₂S₂O₃), iron chloride hexahydrate (FeCl₃·6H₂O), choline chloride ([[(CH₃)₃NCH₂CH₂OH]⁺Cl⁻], urea (CO(NH₂)₂), glycerol (HOCH₂CH(OH)CH₂OH), ethylene glycol (HOCH₂CH₂OH) and citric acid (HOC(COOH)(CH₂COOH)₂) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Switzerland. Agar-agar powder was purchased from Schneitter, Switzerland. As reference cleaning medium, Hagerty silver polish cream was purchased from Puravita, Switzerland.

2.2.1. Complexing solutions and related gel applications

The initial solutions of sodium glycinate (NaGly) and saponin were prepared with the concentrations suggested by literature, i.e., 0.1 M for NaGly and 10 % w/v for saponin [8,25]. The concentration of the initial EDDS trisodium (Na-EDDS) solution as well as that for the initial sodium thiosulphate (Na₂S₂O₃) solution was also 0.1 M, for the purpose of comparison. Na₂S₂O₃ solutions were used as references here, since they are often employed by conservators to remove hard crusts on silver objects [6]. In order to enhance their cleaning effectiveness, the concentrations of these four complexing solutions were further adjusted, as detailed in Table 1. The pH of the 0.5 M NaGly solution was adjusted to 10 as suggested by literature [8]. All solutions were also added to 3 % (w/v) agar-agar powder, magnet stirred at 100 °C until boiling and then cooled down to room temperature to form rigid gels. The prepared gels are presented in Fig. S1 in Supplementary Information (SI).

2.2.2. DESs and DES-based mixtures

FeCl₃·6H₂O-based DESs were prepared by mixing FeCl₃·6H₂O (HBA) and either urea, malonic acid, or ethylene glycol (HBDS) at a molar ratio of 2:1. These reagents were magnet-stirred at 40 °C until transparent, brown liquids were formed [26,27]. The choline chloride:urea (ChCl:U) DES was prepared by mixing the two components and magnet stirring at 100 °C until a colourless, highly viscous liquid was formed. Aquoline was prepared by mixing ChCl and deionized water at a molar ratio of 1:3.33 and magnet stirring at 45 °C until a colourless liquid with low viscosity was obtained [28,29]. Mixing acidic compounds (e.g., metal chlorides, here FeCl₃·6H₂O) and aqueous ChCl-based DESs can act as oxidant (e.g., for the dissolution of lignocellulose biomass) [30,31]. Therefore, the obtained ChCl-U DES and aquoline were further added with 5 % (w/w) FeCl₃·6H₂O and magnet stirred until a light-brown liquid was formed. Such mixtures were expected to function as mild oxidant to alter the silver tarnishing products on the coupons, allowing an ease of removal afterwards.

Inspired by the production of sodium acetate:glycerol DES [32], NaGly-based DESs were prepared by mixing NaGly (HBA) and either glycerol (G) or ethylene Glycol (EG) (HBDS), at a molar ratio of 1:3 and 1:2, magnet stirred at 100 °C for 2 h. The obtained NaGly:G DES was a transparent liquid, with a high viscosity at room temperature, while the NaGly:EG suspension appeared half-transparent and whitish. Deionized water can be added into NaGly:G DES at certain molar ratios to form “water-in-DES” systems [33,34], increasing the fluidity and ease of application. Such water-incorporated DESs appeared half-transparent and can be kept at room temperature for a few months without losing physical stability and cleaning functionality. The same applies to the NaGly:EG suspension.

Table 1

Overview of the four complexing solutions tested.

Complexing solutions	Initial concentration	pH	Modified concentration	pH	Application time
NaGly	0.1 M	11.01	0.5 M	11.39 (adjusted with sulfuric acid to 10)	15 min for solution, 1 h for gel
Na-EDDS	0.1 M	9.30	0.5 M	9.01	
saponin	10 % (w/v)	4.05	20 % (w/v)	3.95	
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃	0.1 M	7.88	0.5 M	7.36	

Table 2

Protocols for the preparation and application of the cleaning media. CA refers to citric acid, ChCl for choline chloride, EG for ethylene glycol, G for glycerol, MA for malonic acid, NaGly for sodium glycinate hydrate, U for urea, and W for water.

Medium type	HBA	HBD	Molar ratio (HBA:HBD)	Additional compound (5 % w/w)	Preparation temperature (°C)	Function	Application method and time
DES	FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	U	2:1	–	40	Oxidant (strong)	Load on Evolon tissues then apply on coupons for 1, 5, 15 and 30 min. Clearance with water
	FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	EG	2:1	–	40		
	FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	MA	2:1	–	40		
	ChCl	U	1:2	FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	100	Oxidant (mild)	
ChCl	W	1:3.33	FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	45			
Suspension	NaGly	G	1:3	–	100	Complexing agent	Cotton swabbing. Clearance with water and ethanol (94 %)
	NaGly	EG	1:2	–	100		
DES	NaGly	CA, G, W	1:1:6:4	–	100	Complexing agent & abrasive	
Slurry	NaGly	CA, G, W	2:1:6:4	–	100		

To increase the complexing capability and fluidity of the NaGly:G DES, citric acid (CA) and deionized water were added at a molar ratio of 1:1:6:4 (NaGly:CA:G:W). The mixture was magnet stirred at 100 °C until a transparent, light brownish liquid was formed. To supplement a mild abrasive function, an additional part of NaGly was added and the final product was a half-transparent, slightly yellowish slurry. Table 2 presents the preparation and application protocols for the above-mentioned DESs. Photos of some prepared cleaning media, including the ChCl:U-FeCl₃·6H₂O mixture, the FeCl₃·6H₂O:EG DES, the suspension and the slurry, are presented in Fig. S2 (SI).

2.3. Cleaning tests

The cleaning tests consisted of three parts: (i) cleaning with the complexing solutions and gels; (ii) cleaning with a two-step method using DESs and/or suspension; (iii) a comparative study between a commercial silver cleaning product, the two-step method and the slurry.

2.3.1. Complexing solutions and gels

The complexing solutions were applied using small pieces (ca. 8 × 8 mm) of Evolon® microfilament tissue, loaded at a ratio of 30 µL per piece; the saturated Evolon pieces were then applied to coupons that had been aged with AS for 3 and 10 h respectively. The application lasted for 15 min, which represents the maximum application time for aqueous solutions applied via Evolon tissues, according to a previous study [35]. The 3 % w/v agar gels loaded with the different complexing solutions were cut into similarly sized pieces (ca. 8 × 8 mm) and then applied to the same types of coupons for 1 h. Schematic illustrations of the application setup are provided in Fig. S3 (SI). After removing the tissues or gels, the treated coupon areas were individually swabbed with dry cotton sticks to eliminate any potential cleaning residues, then cleared with deionized water and ethanol (94 %), and finally hot air dried. The same procedure was repeated for complexing solutions with modified concentrations as well as for the corresponding gels.

2.3.2. Two-step method

The cleaning with the two-step method was performed on coupons aged with AS for 10 h. The process consisted of two steps: (i) tarnish alteration; (ii) removal of the altered tarnish.

Tarnish alteration

The oxidative DESs were loaded on small pieces (ca. 8 × 8 mm) of Evolon tissues on glass slides, at a ratio of 30 µL DES per piece; the loaded tissues were then transferred onto the coupon surfaces. For the mildly oxidative DESs, the application times were set to 30, 60, 90 and 120 min, while for the strongly oxidative DESs, the application times were set to 1, 5, 15 and 30 min. After the removal of Evolon tissues, the coupon areas (each single area at once) were swabbed with dry cotton sticks to remove any DES residues, cleared with deionized water, and then dried with a soft cloth made from 80 % polyester and 20 % polyamide (Coop, Switzerland).

Removal of altered tarnish

The coupon areas pre-treated with the oxidative DESs were swabbed with cotton sticks dipped with the NaGly-based DESs or suspension to remove the altered tarnishing products. Cotton swabbing with deionized water, ethanol and aqueous sodium glycinate solutions (0.1 M and 0.5 M) were also applied onto the pre-treated coupons for comparison. After the tarnish was fully removed, the coupon areas (each single area at once) were further cleaned with deionized water and then ethanol, and finally hot air dried.

2.3.3. Comparative study

The comparative study was performed on sterling silver coupons aged with AS for 15 h. The entire surface of each coupon (both sides) was cleaned using three approaches: (i) a commercial silver polish product (Hagerty silver polish cream) applied via cotton swabbing, (ii) the two-step method described above, and (iii) the NaGly:CA:G:W slurry applied via cotton swabbing. Coupons were weighed using a precision scale (Sartorius) before tarnishing, after tarnishing, and after cleaning to evaluate materials loss during the cleaning process. Each cleaning experiment was performed in triplicate.

2.3.4. Storage of coupons

All unaged, aged, and cleaned coupons were individually placed in brown corrosion interception bags, each containing a corrosion interceptor. The bags were then stored in a closed container at ambient temperature.

2.4. Analytical techniques and experimental parameters

Colorimetry. Colorimetric measurements were performed using an X-Rite Ci6x Spectrophotometer in both SCE (specular component exclusive) and SCI (specular component inclusive) measurement modes. The standard illuminant of D65 and observation angle of 10° were used. The built-in CIE lab colour system was used for the colour analysis, with a commonly accepted Just Noticeable Difference (JND) value of 2.3 [36].

Optical microscopy. OM measurements were performed using a Zeiss Axioskop 2 optical microscope coupled with a Axiocam 305 colour camera in both bright field (BF) and dark field (DF) and Zen core 3.2 software.

Scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy. SEM measurements were performed using a Hitachi Regulus 8230 cold filed emission SEM with 5 keV electron energy in normal incidence with both backscattering and secondary electron detectors. An Ultim Extreme Silicon Drift Detector (SDD) detector from Oxford Instruments, with a detector area of 100 mm², was used for the energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis with Aztec software.

Fourier transformation infrared spectroscopy. FTIR measurements were performed through a Thermo Scientific Nicolet IN10 MX Infrared imaging microscope coupled with a motorized sample stage in ATR mode (Germanium tip ATR crystal). A liquid nitrogen cooled MCT-A detector was used. The spectrum range was 4000–650 cm⁻¹, with a spectral resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. OMNIC Picta software was used for data acquisition and analysis.

Raman spectroscopy. A Renishaw Virsa Raman Analyzer, equipped with two excitation lasers of 532 nm and 785 nm, was used for the Raman measurements. A Nikon LE Plan 50x objective was used for both single-point and mapping measurements, with spectral resolution of ca. 3–4 cm⁻¹. WiRE 5.6 software was used for data acquisition and elaboration. Principle component analysis (PCA) of the map data was performed with MANTIS software [37,38]. Raman integration map spectra were produced from PCA-based cluster spectra. The script for the automatic production of integration map spectra was written in Python.

Interferometric microscopy. IM was employed to obtain direct measurements of surface roughness on both treated and reference coupons. The measurements were conducted using a Keyence VK-X3100 microscope in white light interferometry mode with a 10 × objective lens. The measurements were performed on three areas across each of three different coupons cleaned using each method and the resulting nine sets of parameters were averaged. Prior to extracting roughness parameters, profile background fitting and subtraction were performed using the VK-X3000 MultiFileAnalyzer software to remove surface tilt.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Cleaning with complexing solutions and gels

The application with Evolon tissues loaded with aqueous solutions of saponin (10 %), Na-EDDS (0.1 M), NaGly (0.1 M) and Na₂SO₃ (0.1 M) did not show obvious cleaning effects after 15 min' application. The agar gels loaded with the same solutions showed different optical and physical properties: the agar-saponin gel appeared transparent and brownish, while the other three gels were colourless; the agar-EDDS gel was less rigid at room temperature

than the other three gels. After 60 min' application with the gels, no colour change was observed on the coupons (Fig. 1a). The concentrations of these four solutions and corresponding gels were then increased to 20 % for saponin and 0.5 M for both Na-EDDS, NaGly and Na₂S₂O₃. No significant cleaning effects were observed (Fig. 1b), except for the sterling silver coupon aged for 3 h, where a very slight colour change is noticeable in the areas treated with agar-saponin (20 %), agar-NaGly (0.5 M) and agar-Na₂S₂O₃ (0.5 M) for 60 min (Fig. 1b, within the red frame). Such observations indicate that copper complexing agents may not be as efficient on the silver tarnish containing Ag-Cu-S products or longer application time is needed.

With the 0.5 M Na-EDDS solution, a rigid gel cannot be formed. A drop of the soft gel was thus placed on the coupons. After 1 hour's application, the Na-EDDS gel fully dried while the other gels retained their initial shape and elasticity. Furthermore, the colour of the NaGly gel changed from its initial light brownish to more colourless, when the 0.5 M solution (pH10) was used. It is uncertain yet whether the pH or the concentration of the solution caused the colour change.

3.2. Cleaning with the two-step method

Tarnish alteration

Both the ChCl:U-FeCl₃ and aquoline-FeCl₃ mixtures caused a slight colour change (indicator of tarnish alteration) of the coupon surface after application. While the aquoline-FeCl₃ mixtures showed a low viscosity, which helped loading onto Evolon tissues, the ChCl:U-FeCl₃ mixture gave a more homogeneous appearance of the treated coupon's areas, despite a relatively slow loading rate on the tissues. The ChCl:U-FeCl₃ mixture was thus selected for further tests with extended application times of 30, 60, 90 and 120 min.

In contrast, the application of FeCl₃·6H₂O-based DESs resulted in a fast colour change of the coupon surface. Of three such DESs tested, the FeCl₃·6H₂O:U DES had a high viscosity and was thus difficult to load; The FeCl₃·6H₂O:MA DES was very acidic and aggressive, which may damage the substrate materials. The FeCl₃·6H₂O:EG DES showed a low viscosity and a moderate alteration rate and was thus selected for further tests with extended application times of 1, 5, 15 and 30 min.

Fig. 2a presents Raman integration map spectra of all four areas treated with the FeCl₃·6H₂O:EG DES, compared to that of an untreated area. A broad band centred at ca. 251 cm⁻¹, related to Ag-Cu-S products, of the untreated area disappeared, while relatively sharp band centred at ca. 239 cm⁻¹ coupled with a shoulder band at ca. 150 cm⁻¹ appeared in each case, which can be attributed to AgCl as reported in literature [39] and also agrees with the reference AgCl powder spectrum (Fig. 2a). This observation indicates that after treatment with FeCl₃·6H₂O:EG DES, the tarnish composition has transformed from Ag-Cu-S compounds to AgCl. In contrast, sterling silver coupon area treated with ChCl:U-FeCl₃ for 120 min gave a Raman spectrum similar to that of the untreated area, with a broad band centred at ca. 247 cm⁻¹. Notably, after the treatment with ChCl:U-FeCl₃, a shoulder band at ca. 313 cm⁻¹ (likely chalcocite Cu₂S [24]) and a weak band at ca. 475 cm⁻¹ (likely covellite CuS [39,40]) were observed, which can indicate that the tarnishing products have been transformed into more Cu-rich products after the alteration step.

Raman integration map spectra of a pure silver coupon treated with the FeCl₃·6H₂O:EG DES are presented in Fig. 2bA broad band centred at ca. 237 cm⁻¹ can be observed in the spectra of the areas treated for 5, 15 and 30 min, indicating the formation of AgCl. The spectra of the untreated area and the area treated for 1 min exhibit a similar Raman spectrum, showing a band at around 218 cm⁻¹ and a weak band at ca. 455 cm⁻¹, which indicates an oxidation of

Fig. 1. Photos of silver coupons treated with gels: (a) gels loaded with complexing solutions of initial concentrations; (b) gels loaded with complexing solutions of increased concentrations. The coupon showing slight colour changes is indicated with the red frame.

Fig. 2. Raman integration map spectra of silver coupons aged with AS for 10 h. (a) from bottom to top, sterling silver coupons: untreated, treated with the FeCl₃·6H₂O:EG DES for 1, 5, 15 and 30 min, compared to a coupon treated with the ChCl:U-FeCl₃ mixture for 120 min; (b) from bottom to top, pure silver coupons: untreated, treated with the FeCl₃·6H₂O:EG DES for 1, 5, 15 and 30 min, compared to a sterling silver coupon treated with the same DES for 1 min. Reference spectrum of AgCl powder is also showed.

tarnishing products during measurements. Indeed, Ag₂S, the main tarnishing product of pure silver, is highly photosensitive and can be easily oxidized under laser excitation. This observation further indicates that while a one-minute application of FeCl₃·6H₂O:EG DES is sufficient to transform Ag-Cu-S products into AgCl on the

tested sterling silver coupon, a longer treatment time is required to achieve the transformation of Ag₂S into AgCl on pure silver. This is consistent with our observation that tarnish on sterling silver coupons was easier and faster to remove using the two-step method, compared to pure silver coupons.

Removal of altered tarnish

Cotton swabbing with deionized water and ethanol did not remove any tarnishing products formed in the alteration step, which confirmed our hypothesis that a complexing agent was needed for the removal of the altered tarnish. The same applied to the aqueous NaGly solutions, suggesting that it is necessary to use high concentration. Compared to the NaGly:G DES and the NaGly:CA:G:W slurry, the NaGly:EG suspension worked faster and more thoroughly on the altered tarnish and was thus selected for the tarnish removal step. We also noted that the slurry can be directly used for the tarnish removal without the alteration step, likely due to its abrasive properties. Neither the NaGly:G DES nor the suspension worked on the tarnish that has not been previously treated with the alteration step.

Fig. 3 presents the two-step method on both sterling and pure silver coupons aged for 10 h. No cleaning effects were observed on the coupons treated with first ChCl:U-FeCl_3 mixture and then the NaGly:EG suspension, while on the coupons treated with first $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O:EG}$ DES and then the NaGly:EG suspension, obvious cleaning effects were observed for all four treated areas. The successful removal of AgCl with the suspension was likely due to a lower lattice energy (i.e., 910 kJ/mol [41]), compared to that of Ag_2S (i.e. 2606 kJ/mol [41]) and possibly that of Ag-Cu-S as well (no data from literature so far), which made the dissolution and complexation of Ag ions easier. It is worth mentioning that these two steps need to be performed sequentially within a short time to achieve optimal cleaning results.

The identification of possible complexation products was performed with FTIR spectroscopy on the cotton sticks that were used to remove the altered tarnish on the coupons indicated in Fig. 3b. Reference spectrum of NaGly:EG and NaGly powder are shown in Fig. S4 (SI). Although previous studies reported that it is difficult to unambiguously attribute IR vibrational bands to silver-glycinate complexes [7], some band shifts were observed between reference spectra of NaGly, NaGly:EG and that on the cotton sticks. For example, a band shift from 1045 cm^{-1} in the NaGly:EG spectrum to 1053 cm^{-1} in the spectra of cotton sticks may suggest that some chemical changes associated with the amino groups occurred [42]. Note that an adjacent band at around 1032 cm^{-1} in the spectra of cotton sticks possibly refers to the cotton fibre [43]. Such cotton sticks were also analysed with SEM-EDX. However, due to the strong charging and outgassing issues, only one stick worked on the pure silver coupon provided some limited information. More information is presented in SI.

3.3. Comparative study

The Hagerty silver polish cream demonstrated moderate cleaning efficiency but resulted in noticeable scratches on the coupon surface and a slightly over-polished appearance. Depending on the applied area, the cleaning rate of the two-step method varied, i.e., it was relatively fast in the central area of the coupons but relatively slower along the edges. Furthermore, the coupon surface cleaned with the two-step method appeared somewhat whitish, suggesting slight surface roughening. Despite its low cleaning rate (at least three times slower than the Hagerty cream), the custom slurry produced the best cleaning results: no significant surface roughening, scratches or over-polishing were observed.

3.3.1. Weight loss assessment

Table 3 presents the weight of coupons before aging, after aging and after cleaning. The material loss of the coupons cleaned with the Hagerty cream and the slurry was similar (0.03 % vs. 0.04 %), while the two-step method resulted in a relatively higher material loss of about 0.15 %.

3.3.2. Colour measurements

Colorimetric values in the SCE mode, which is closer to human perceptions [44], are presented in Fig. 4. The coupon cleaned with the two-step method had the largest colour difference (i.e., ΔE^*ab value of 34.52 ± 0.93), compared to the control (i.e., untarnished) coupon. This is mainly due to the high L^* value (81.46 ± 0.62), indicating a high diffuse light reflection caused by a rough surface [45]. On the contrary, the L^* value of the coupon cleaned with Hagerty cream (44.33 ± 0.35) was even lower than that of the control coupon (48.04 ± 0.43), indicating a lower diffuse light reflection or a higher specular light reflection. Such observations were compatible with the visual observations that the coupon cleaned with the two-step method appeared slightly whitish and the coupon cleaned with the Hagerty cream was somewhat over-polished. The coupons cleaned with the slurry showed marginally higher L^* (50.72 ± 0.87) and b^* values (0.15 ± 0.16) than the control coupon, indicating that the surface of this coupon became slightly rougher, and its colour changed towards the direction of yellow. Tabular data of colorimetric values are presented in Table S1 in SI.

3.3.3. Surface roughness measurements

IM measurements confirmed the hypothesis proposed based on the visual and colorimetric observations. Although the coupons cleaned with Hagerty cream exhibited arithmetic mean height (S_a) and root mean square height (S_q) values similar to those of the control coupon, their maximum height (S_z) - defined as the vertical distance from the highest point to the deepest valley - was significantly lower, indicating a reduction in extreme vertical surface features [46]. This suggests that the cream smoothed out some of the original surface features on the coupons, potentially accounting for their slightly over-polished appearance. In comparison, the coupons cleaned with the slurry showed slightly elevated S_a and S_q values and a lower S_z value relative to the control, suggesting mild surface abrasion with minimal introduction of deep features. The highest roughness values were observed for the coupons cleaned with the two-step method, with S_a and S_q values about three times greater than those of the control, and a slightly increased S_z value, indicating both general and localized surface roughening (Table 4).

3.3.4. Observations via optical microscopy

The aforementioned colour nuances and surface roughness could not be accurately captured using standard photography (Fig. 5a–d), due to the strong specular reflection from the cleaned coupon surfaces. However, OM images revealed some differences in the surface micro-structures. The OM-BF and -DF images of representative coupons for each cleaning method are shown in Fig. 5e–l. The coupon cleaned with the Hagerty cream exhibited distinct scratches (horizontal lines in Fig. 5f, j), likely caused by the abrasive particles embedded in the cream, while a coupon cleaned with the two-step method exhibited numerous fine pits on the surface (Fig. 5g, k), consistent with the roughness measurements. No significant scratches or pits were observed on the coupon cleaned with the slurry, although the original rolling marks from the manufacture, which are observable in the images of the control coupon (Fig. 5e, i), were reduced by the slurry (Fig. 5h, l).

3.3.5. Observations via scanning electron microscopy

SEM secondary electron (SE) and backscattered (BSE) imaging further confirmed the OM observations. Fig. 6 shows the SEM images of the representative coupons examined with OM. Hagerty cream smoothed some initial, small surface features (b, g) that can be observed on the control coupon (a, f), and scratches on the surface can be clearly observed. In the SEM images of the coupon cleaned with the two-step method, we observed a mixture of two

Table 3
Average weight change of the tested sterling silver coupons during the aging and cleaning processes.

Cleaning method	Weight before aging (g)	Weight after aging (g)	Weight after cleaning (g)	Weight loss ratio (wt%)
Hagerty cream	2.2365 ± 0.0901	2.2367 ± 0.0903	2.2359 ± 0.0901	0.0284 ± 0.0059
Two-step method	2.2947 ± 0.0159	2.2950 ± 0.0163	2.2914 ± 0.0175	0.1456 ± 0.0702
Slurry	2.2372 ± 0.0610	2.2375 ± 0.0611	2.2363 ± 0.0610	0.0387 ± 0.0270

Fig. 3. Photographs of sterling and pure silver coupons cleaned with the two-step method: (a) coupons cleaned with the ChCl₃:U-FeCl₃ mixture combined with the NaGly:EG suspension; (b) coupons cleaned with the FeCl₃:EG DES combined with the NaGly:EG suspension.

Fig. 4. Charts of colorimetric values in the SCE mode for the control coupon and the coupons cleaned with the Hagerty cream, two-step method and slurry.

Table 4
Surface roughness data obtained from IM measurements for the control coupon and the coupons cleaned with the Hagerty cream, two-step method and slurry.

Cleaning method	Sa (μm)	Sz (μm)	Sq (μm)
Control	0.045 ± 0.006	2.334 ± 0.645	0.073 ± 0.006
Hagerty cream	0.049 ± 0.007	1.476 ± 0.154	0.077 ± 0.010
Two-step method	0.153 ± 0.007	2.527 ± 0.376	0.204 ± 0.007
Slurry	0.064 ± 0.007	2.204 ± 0.177	0.100 ± 0.009

types of surface features. An extreme case representing the pits can be observed in Fig. 6c and h, while a relatively flat surface is observable in Fig. 6d and i. Both SE and BSE images of the coupon cleaned with the slurry (e, j) showed the closest surface features to those of the control coupon.

Finally, it is worth noting that the roughened surface resulting from the two-step method can be smoothed using the NaGly:CA:G:W slurry due to its finely abrasive properties, through which an optimal cleaning effect can be achieved. A potential advantage of using the two-step method lies in its better control.

Fig. 5. Photographs and OM images of the control coupon (a, e, i) and coupons cleaned with the Hagerty cream (b, f, j), the two-step method (c, g, k) and the customized slurry (d, h, l): photographs acquired with a conventional camera (a-d), OM-BF images (e-h), and OM-DF images (i-l). Original OM magnification: 20x. Scale bar: 50 μm .

Fig. 6. SEM images of the control and a representative coupon for each cleaning method: SE and BSE images are shown for the control coupon (a, f), the coupon cleaned with Hagerty cream (b, g), the coupon cleaned with the two-step method showing a relatively rough surface (c, h), the coupons cleaned with the two-step method showing a relatively smooth surface (d, i) and the coupon cleaned with the custom slurry (e, j). Original magnification: 5000x. Scale bar: 10 μm .

For example, we have observed that once the AgCl layer was consumed, it was necessary to repeat the first step to continue the cleaning. In contrast, cleaning with abrasive products (e.g., Hagerty cream) can reach beyond the tarnish layer and remove material from the silver substrate, as the removed materials were consistently dark. This made it difficult to clearly determine when the silver substrate was reached. After the final clearance with water and ethanol, no cleaning residues were observed on the coupon surfaces.

4. Conclusion

This article presents a preliminary study of greener materials including deep eutectic solvents (DESS) for the cleaning of silver tarnish. The application of micro-filament tissues (Evolon)

loaded with aqueous solutions of saponin, sodium glycinate, EDDS and sodium thiosulphate did not show substantial cleaning effects, likely due to the short application time of the tissues (i.e., 15 min) as well as the complexing capabilities more favouring Cu ions than Ag ions. The same applied to the application of agar gels loaded with such complexing agents, although the application time for gels was extended to one hour.

In contrast, the application of a two-step method showed an efficient cleaning for heavy tarnish on both sterling and pure silver coupons. In the first step, the use of oxidative DESs or DES mixtures can result in the alteration of the tarnish layer towards more soluble tarnishing products. Raman measurements showed that AgCl was the main product present after the alteration step, which can be further removed by the second step of cotton swabbing with sodium glycinate-based suspension, likely due to the

complexing capability of glycinate and lower lattice energy of AgCl (compared to Ag₂S and Ag-Cu-S compounds). However, both visual observations and analytical results of the coupon surfaces treated with the two-step method indicated slight surface roughening, which could be further smoothed by applying a slurry prepared by mixing sodium glycinate, citric acid, glycerol and deionized water. This slurry can also be directly used for the removal of silver tarnish, providing a cleaning appearance that is closer to the untarnished coupon. No significant materials loss was observed by applying the slurry.

Despite the surface roughening, the two-step method was effective in removing heavy tarnish with a moderate cleaning rate. The cleaning action can also be controlled by introducing a manageable alteration of the tarnish layer in the first step, minimizing the risk of continuously cleaning by abrasive methods. Furthermore, it can be applied on silver objects with curved surfaces, when delivered with flexible loading matrix (e.g., tissues). Future studies will focus on the optimization of the protocols (e.g., using controlled but efficient DESs or mixtures for the tarnish alteration step) as well as the identification and characterisation of the Ag complexes. Meanwhile, the cleaning mechanisms of the custom slurry will be further investigated; its preparation and application protocols will be developed to increase the cleaning rate.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.culher.2025.08.002.

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